

The Effectiveness of Solar Photovoltaic Energy Policies in Dubai and Abu Dhabi

Mourad Hamdi

Extension School, Harvard University

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Professor Nazeli Tonoyan

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Climate change and resource depletion have been affecting the world for several centuries (Locke et al., 2023). Climate change, defined as changes in temperatures and weather patterns over an extended period, is primarily attributed to increased greenhouse gas emissions resulting from human activity, particularly the heavy exploitation of natural resources (Fawzy et al., 2020; Yoro & Daramola, 2020). Greenhouse gases are gases in the Earth's atmosphere that trap heat. To mitigate these effects, within the next century, global energy systems must transition to technologies that produce less carbon dioxide (Alharbi & Csala, 2021; Fawzy et al., 2020). This imperative has driven countries worldwide to investigate low-carbon and sustainable energy choices, as confronting climate change through transformative energy policies has never been more urgent (Alhammami & An, 2020).

The United Arab Emirates (UAE) is undergoing a strategic shift toward renewable energy, driven by its recognition of the necessity to transition away from traditional fossil fuels and embrace sustainable, clean energy sources (Praveen et al., 2020). The Dubai Electricity and Water Authority aims to generate 75% of its energy from renewable sources by 2050 (Suri et al., 2022). The Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar power plant in Dubai is one of the most significant solar projects globally, with a planned capacity of 5,000 megawatts (MW) by 2030. This facility is expected to reduce carbon emissions by 6.5 million tons annually (Obaideen et al., 2021). Abu Dhabi has also made significant progress in renewable energy, developing the world's largest single-site solar plant, the Noor Abu Dhabi project. This 1.17 GW plant can power 90,000 households and reduce carbon emissions by 1 million tons annually (Frag & Bansal, 2022). These solar photovoltaic (PV) initiatives, which convert sunlight into electrical

energy, represent a broader commitment to environmental and economic diversification (Hussain et al., 2022).

Amid the global environmental crisis, the UAE's commitment to energy diversification and sustainability through solar PV initiatives constitutes a unique model of regional adaptation (Shareef & Altan, 2019). This study compares the respective solar energy policies of Dubai and Abu Dhabi, an area unexplored in previous literature. By adopting a comparative methodology and stakeholder analysis, it aims to illustrate the nuances of the regulatory frameworks and stakeholder dynamics that result in successful solar energy projects. The findings have broader implications for global renewable energy strategies and offer a novel understanding of the efficacy of the solar PV policies of the two cities, providing valuable data for policymakers and stakeholders to enhance the UAE's energy sustainability (Salimi et al., 2022).

Dubai and Abu Dhabi, the two most prominent cities in the UAE, have each implemented a distinct solar PV policy to diversify their energy resources (Ramachandran et al., 2022). Given solar power's potential to meet energy demands sustainably (Griffiths & Orkoubi, 2018), the adoption and expansion of solar PV energy are crucial to the national vision of energy diversification and sustainability to which both cities have committed (Murooshid, 2018). Nonetheless, although the two cities share objectives, they have adopted different policy frameworks with unique priorities and strategies regarding solar energy development (Praveen et al., 2020).

This paper investigates how effectively the solar PV policies of Dubai and Abu Dhabi encourage solar energy development, how the engagement strategies of the cities' stakeholders differ in the context of solar PV energy policies, and the potential impact these differences will have on project outcomes. It contends that understanding the challenges posed by regulatory

frameworks and stakeholder engagement will be essential as Dubai and Abu Dhabi seek to create favorable environments for ongoing investment and expansion in this area (Al Naqbi et al., 2019). By assessing how successfully each city has implemented its energy goals, this paper provides valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of their respective policies (Al-Sarihi & Mansouri, 2022). It is clear that regulatory frameworks have influenced the development and implementation of energy policies. By dissecting two differing strategic approaches within the same national context, this study provides a nuanced understanding of policy efficacy. This comparative framework demonstrates how unique combinations of regulatory mechanisms and stakeholder dynamics can influence the scalability and success of renewable energy projects (Alsalman et al., 2023). Such insights are invaluable for global policy advisors and stakeholders, offering possibilities for assessing and refining solar energy policies in other regions. Moreover, by comparing and contrasting Dubai's and Abu Dhabi's solar PV initiatives, this paper reveals how these strategies align with the UAE's broader renewable energy goals and assesses their potential to shape the future of sustainable development (Nedaei et al., 2022), offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of solar PV energy policies.

The study begins with an introductory section that lays the groundwork and explains the main objective of the research. It briefly considers the historical context, relevant theoretical frameworks, and existing literature to extract essential insights and identify gaps in the current body of knowledge. It then outlines the research methodology used to gather, select, and analyze data from the available secondary sources. It continues by presenting the main findings thematically, emphasizing the environmental impact, economic consequences, and implications for energy security of Dubai's and Abu Dhabi's solar PV energy policies. The subsequent discussion section contextualizes these observations, explores their broader implications, and

identifies the study's limitations. The final section summarizes the main findings and emphasizes the need for further investigation into the implementation and scalability of solar PV projects in the context of evolving global and regional energy policies.

Background, Theoretical Frameworks, and Existing Research

The transition to renewable energy, specifically solar PV energy, is an essential component of the worldwide drive to address climate change and reduce reliance on fossil fuels (Fawzy et al., 2020). In the UAE, Dubai and Abu Dhabi are leading this transition by introducing a number of policies to encourage the adoption and effective utilization of solar energy. This paper seeks to identify gaps in the existing literature and suggest areas for further research by reviewing the historical context; theoretical frameworks concerning sustainability, energy security, and economic growth; and policy outcomes relating to the energy transition. This study contends that understanding the challenges posed by regulatory frameworks and stakeholder engagement will be essential as Dubai and Abu Dhabi seek to create favorable environments for ongoing solar PV energy investment and expansion (Al Naqbi et al., 2019). In this context, this section introduces the hypothesis that Dubai's solar PV policy framework may be more effective than Abu Dhabi's.

The Energy Transition

In the early 2000s, in response to global concerns over climate change, the UAE began transitioning to renewable energy sources (Munawwar & Ghedira, 2014). Subsequently, Dubai and Abu Dhabi have implemented ambitious policies to diversify their energy sources, with solar PV energy playing a significant role due to the weather conditions of the region. These policies exemplify a significant societal transition toward sustainability, driven by economic, environmental, and social considerations (Praveen et al., 2020). The question of how to meet the

renewable energy targets for 2030 has nonetheless been a contentious issue in both Dubai and Abu Dhabi, particularly in relation to solar PV energy policy (Al Naqbi et al., 2019).

Some analysts have argued that the region's abundance of fossil fuels has acted as a barrier to the widespread implementation of solar PV technologies. From this perspective, the low cost of oil and gas, which satisfy the requirements for domestic energy, has discouraged investment in renewable energy sources (Fawzy et al., 2020). Others, however, contend that Dubai and Abu Dhabi are being driven to adopt a solar PV energy policy through a combination of economic, governmental, and climatic factors (Frag & Bansal, 2022). Leading advocates of solar PV energy argue that these factors necessitate the diversification of energy sources and the reduction of carbon emissions (Alharbi & Csala, 2021). From this perspective, the primary challenge in deploying solar PV technologies is striking a balance between economic costs and benefits, which should also be integral parts of the equation. When it comes to determining the most effective policy approach to reach this goal, however, consensus remains elusive. While some believe that financial incentives such as subsidies and feed-in tariffs are the best option, others argue for mandatory renewable energy targets and stakeholder engagement (Ramachandran et al., 2022). Alsalman et al. (2023) argued that net metering is the most effective policy mechanism for encouraging renewable energy use in the UAE because it is economically viable for both customers and electrical utilities. In contrast, Praveen et al. (2020) emphasized the need for broad policy initiatives and incentives regarding solar PV energy. They also stressed the importance of analyzing the social, political, and economic factors that drive renewable energy adoption, moving the focus beyond customer-oriented policies.

Theoretical Frameworks

Sustainability and Energy Security

Analysis of the effectiveness of solar PV energy regulations in Dubai and Abu Dhabi requires a theoretical framework that combines the principles of sustainability, energy security, and economic growth (Alharbi & Csala, 2021). Among these, the element of sustainability must be prioritized in order to assess the effectiveness of the policies in managing current energy needs while simultaneously preserving economic growth. Within this context, specific policies can be evaluated for their capacity to reduce emissions and promote solar PV energy use (Salimi et al., 2022), both of which are essential for sustainable development. A further question concerns whether specific measures enhance the stability and independence of energy supplies (Hafeznia et al., 2017). The UAE's shift toward solar PV energy represents a deliberate effort to reduce reliance on fossil fuels as a means of protecting against fluctuations in energy supply and the uncertainties of global geopolitics (Al-Sarihi & Mansouri, 2022). Building on this, it is possible to assess whether and if the solar PV energy policies enhance the energy self-sufficiency of both cities.

Energy Security and Economic Growth

Economic theories about growth and diversification offer insight into the impact of policies on the economy. While the implementation of solar infrastructure involves a substantial up-front expense, the potential long-term economic benefits, such as improved cost-effectiveness and energy price stability, are enormous (Sgouridis et al., 2016). However, the effectiveness of this implementation depends on the active involvement of stakeholders, including the

government. The question at hand, therefore, is how stakeholders influence the implementation and efficacy of solar PV energy policies in Dubai and Abu Dhabi.

The theoretical framework described above provides a comprehensive model for understanding the solar PV energy policies of Dubai and Abu Dhabi. By focusing on sustainability, energy security, and economic growth, it establishes a solid basis for evaluating the efficacy of the policies concerned. It also emphasizes the importance of stakeholder cooperation in achieving the goal of transitioning to sustainable energy.

Existing Literature

Environmental and Technological Drivers of Solar PV Energy Deployment

Most existing research on this topic adopts a mixed-methods approach, with researchers generally agreeing that adopting renewable energy is crucial for the sustainable development of Dubai and Abu Dhabi (Alsaman et al., 2023; Praveen et al., 2020). Recommendations differ, however, on the best strategies for achieving this goal. Thus, while both studies recognize environmental protection and technological advancement as significant factors affecting deployment, their emphasis differs. This suggests that adopting a comprehensive and tailored approach is essential for integrating renewable energy, emphasizing the connection between economic viability and technological advancement.

Challenges of Solar PV Policies

Recent literature has highlighted the growing implementation of solar PV systems in the UAE (Alsaman et al., 2023; Praveen et al., 2020). Other studies have shown that the policies established have increased the use of renewable energy sources, reducing carbon emissions and fossil fuel demand (Shareef & Altan, 2019). However, challenges remain, including economic

and financial barriers, regulatory hurdles, and the need for market infrastructure improvements (Al Naqbi et al., 2019).

Microgrid Development and Policy Frameworks

Sajwani et al. (2023) expanded the discourse on the UAE's microgrid development and provided a review of policy frameworks. Whereas Fawzy et al. (2020) and Munawwar and Ghedira (2014) presented a positive outlook regarding the challenges of solar energy, Sajwani et al. (2023) delivered a more critical assessment of the present situation, emphasizing the urgent need for more robust policy frameworks. This mixture of perspectives sheds light on the concerted efforts toward sustainable energy production in Dubai and Abu Dhabi and the challenges involved in such energy transitions. Scholars have long argued that subsidies are all-important for the initial uptake of solar PV technologies (Hayati et al., 2023). New research, however, has suggested otherwise, proposing that in fact, a combination of policy instruments, including both incentives and regulations, yields the most effective and sustainable results (Aghahosseini et al., 2020; Al Naqbi et al., 2019; Alnaser et al., 2022).

Research Gap

The existing literature on energy transitions in Dubai and Abu Dhabi has extensively examined the policies implemented to date, especially those promoting solar PV energy. However, there remains a gap in the literature regarding a thorough investigation of the effectiveness of solar PV policies in the UAE. Such research would provide crucial information

to enable policymakers and stakeholders to make informed decisions, which could help enhance the UAE's overall solar PV energy plan.

Methodology

This study applies a desktop-based methodology to examine scholarly articles published between 2014 and 2023. Through comparative analysis, it evaluates the effectiveness of the solar PV policies adopted by Dubai and Abu Dhabi and their implications for sustainable energy development. Drawing on these sources, the study focuses on capturing a broad spectrum of insights into policy development, implementation, and outcomes. To ensure high reliability and validity, the sources cited were evaluated based on reputation, methodology, and research recognition (i.e., the number of times cited in other publications). The study prioritized documents that met scholarly standards and contributed directly to the understanding of solar PV policy effectiveness within the context of the UAE's energy strategy. A thematic approach was adopted for the data analysis, which entailed identifying, examining, and recording recurrent themes within the collected data. This facilitated the delineation of similarities and divergences in strategic approaches, stakeholder engagement, and environmental and economic impact. Overall, this comprehensive methodology ensures that the study's findings are rooted in credible evidence and reflect the nuanced policy landscapes of Dubai and Abu Dhabi. Each city's distinct solar energy strategy is identified and key aspects contributing to successful sustainable energy initiatives are emphasized.

This approach will help clarify the policy priorities, strategies, and objectives of Dubai's Clean Energy Strategy 2050 and Abu Dhabi's National Energy Strategy 2030. By prioritizing documentary evidence and qualitative data analysis, it will offer a clear understanding of the complexities of solar PV energy policymaking and implementation. The study's methodological

novelty lies in its desktop-based comparative approach and stakeholder analysis, which together offer a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of the examined solar PV policies.

Through robust qualitative data analysis, this novel approach allows for a close examination of not only policymaking but also stakeholder engagement, providing a replicable model for similar assessments in diverse geopolitical contexts, thereby potentially fostering a more global understanding of energy policy dynamics.

Findings

This section aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these policies by comparing and contrasting the approaches taken in Dubai and Abu Dhabi. Additionally, it aims to investigate the differences between the policies that may not be readily apparent.

Dubai's Solar PV Policies

Dubai's solar PV policies, exemplified by initiatives such as Shams Dubai and the Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park development, demonstrate a comprehensive approach to integrating renewable energy into Dubai's power grid. The effectiveness of these policies can be assessed by evaluating their capacity to meet Dubai's Clean Energy Strategy 2050 targets, stimulate stakeholder engagement, and foster innovation and sustainability in the energy sector.

The Shams Dubai Initiative

A pivotal element of Dubai's renewable energy strategy, the Shams Dubai initiative facilitates the widespread adoption of solar energy by allowing homeowners, businesses, and industrial entities to install solar panels and connect them to the grid. This initiative promotes energy independence among residents and businesses and contributes significantly to Dubai's

goal of producing 75% of its energy from clean sources by 2050 (Abuzaid et al., 2022). The success of Shams Dubai can be attributed to its direct impact on reducing electricity bills for participants and its role in enhancing grid resilience and sustainability. By converting buildings into micro-generators, Shams Dubai effectively decentralizes energy production for companies and individuals. The initiative has installed PV panels on 1,032 buildings, with a total capacity of 43.77 MW. This will increase in the future and eventually cover all buildings in Dubai by 2030, fostering a culture of sustainability and self-sufficiency (Abuzaid et al., 2022).

Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park

Set to become the world's largest single-site solar power plant, the Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park project exemplifies Dubai's ambitious approach to clean energy production. With a planned capacity of 5,000 MW by 2030, the solar plant is a key element of Dubai's strategic commitment to transitioning to renewable energy (Salimi et al., 2022).

Moreover, its role extends beyond electricity generation. The plant is also a center for solar research and innovation, attracting international collaboration and investment in clean energy technologies. The solar park's contribution to Dubai's clean energy goals and its impact on reducing carbon emissions affirm the effectiveness of Dubai's solar PV policies in achieving large-scale, strategic renewable energy outcomes. Specifically, the solar park will save more than 6.5 million tons of carbon emissions each year (Obaideen et al., 2021).

Sustainable Development Goals

Dubai's ambitious solar PV energy policies, exemplified by the initiatives described above, align closely with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action). These policies contribute

significantly to achieving these goals by promoting the widespread adoption of clean energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and fostering innovation and growth in the renewable energy sector (Obaideen et al., 2021). Dubai's solar PV energy policies are effective because they take a comprehensive approach to achieving sustainability and clean energy goals. Through initiatives such as Shams Dubai and the Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park, Dubai has successfully created a robust framework for renewable energy adoption characterized by innovation, stakeholder engagement, and a solid commitment to environmental stewardship. These initiatives contribute to Dubai's clean energy objectives and position it as a leader in the global transition to sustainable energy.

Stakeholder Engagement and Regulatory Frameworks

The regulatory framework of the Shams Dubai initiative serves as a cornerstone for Dubai's renewable energy strategy, as it is specifically designed to encourage the adoption of solar energy across various sectors. This framework simplifies the solar panel installation process by streamlining applications, approvals, and connections to the power grid (Abuzaid et al., 2022). The success of the initiative hinges on its ability to engage a diverse range of stakeholders, including homeowners, businesses, and industrial operators, thereby fostering a culture of inclusivity and decentralization in energy production. By enabling buildings to produce their own renewable energy, the Shams Dubai initiative reduces dependence on fossil fuels, lowers carbon emissions, and showcases Dubai's commitment to environmental and sustainable development (Hussain et al., 2022). The regulatory framework has also been

designed to be dynamic, incorporating feedback from stakeholders to ensure that policies remain effective and responsive to the community's needs and the evolving energy landscape.

Challenges and Opportunities for Policy Adjustment

As Dubai continues to push the boundaries of its renewable energy capacity, it faces the dual challenge of keeping up with both rapid technological advancements and evolving financial models in the solar energy sector. To address these challenges, Dubai can leverage international partnerships and embrace cutting-edge technologies. An illustrative case of international collaboration is the efficacy of the partnership between the Dubai Electricity and Water Authority and the International Renewable Energy Agency, which aims to promote renewable energy deployment and support the development and implementation of solar PV energy policies and regulatory frameworks for accelerating renewable energy (Alnaser et al., 2022).

The evolution of Dubai's solar energy policies presents a significant opportunity for policy adjustment and innovation. By embracing technological advancements, exploring new financial models, and strengthening international collaborations, Dubai can enhance the effectiveness of its solar PV energy policies, thereby making solar energy more cost-effective and accessible for all stakeholders (Aghahosseini et al., 2020).

Abu Dhabi's Solar PV Policies

Abu Dhabi's approach to solar PV energy policies is characterized by an emphasis on large-scale strategic projects such as Noor Abu Dhabi and the Al Dhafra Solar PV Project. These initiatives underscore the city's commitment to clean energy and reflect its strategy of taking a leadership role in the renewable energy sector by leveraging its resources and partnerships. The

effectiveness of these policies is reflected in their contribution to Abu Dhabi's energy mix, the reduction of carbon emissions, and the fostering of innovation and economic diversification.

Noor Abu Dhabi

A symbol of Abu Dhabi's renewable energy journey, the Noor Abu Dhabi Solar Power Plant is one of the world's most significant solar projects, with a capacity of 1.17 GW (Praveen et al., 2020). The plant contributes significantly to the UAE's clean energy targets, providing enough electricity to power 90,000 households across 259,000 houses (Salimi et al., 2022). Its success highlights the effectiveness of Abu Dhabi's policies in achieving scalability and reliability in renewable energy production. Furthermore, by achieving one of the world's lowest costs for solar power, Noor Abu Dhabi sets a standard for the economic viability of solar energy, emphasizing the strategic impact of Abu Dhabi's investment in clean energy technologies (Ramachandran et al., 2022).

Al Dhafra Solar PV Project

Set to surpass Noor Abu Dhabi in terms of capacity, the Al Dhafra Solar PV power plant exemplifies Abu Dhabi's ongoing commitment to expanding its renewable energy portfolio. This project is expected to play a critical role in meeting Abu Dhabi's clean energy goals, further reducing reliance on fossil fuels and decreasing carbon emissions (Wang et al., 2023). The project demonstrates Abu Dhabi's ability to execute large-scale renewable energy projects and its effectiveness in attracting international investment from France and China and fostering partnerships with two local players, Taqa and Masdar, and two international investors, EDF Renewables and Jinko Power, in the clean energy sector (Salimi et al., 2022). Furthermore, such initiatives are integral to Abu Dhabi's economic diversification efforts. By investing in

renewable energy, Abu Dhabi not only reduces its carbon footprint but also fosters new industries and job opportunities in the clean energy sector. This approach aligns with the broader vision of economic sustainability, highlighting the effectiveness of solar PV policies in contributing to a sustainable economy.

Sustainable Development Goals

Abu Dhabi's approach to solar PV energy, highlighted by the projects described above, resonates with the SDGs, particularly SDGs 7 and 13. These projects emphasize Abu Dhabi's commitment to clean energy and climate action, demonstrating its efforts to transition to a sustainable energy future (Obaideen et al., 2021).

Stakeholder Engagement and Regulatory Frameworks

Abu Dhabi's strategic approach to renewable energy emphasizes large-scale solar projects, a direction that leverages its vast resources and strategic partnerships with leading global energy companies. By adopting the independent power producer model, Abu Dhabi has successfully financed and operationalized significant projects, such as the two described above (Salimi et al., 2022). The partnerships that have facilitated these projects highlight Abu Dhabi's commitment to renewable energy and emphasize its significance as a critical player in the global energy market. The Abu Dhabi Department of Energy plays a pivotal role in this energy system, crafting regulations that support massive investment while ensuring the environmental and economic sustainability of the resulting endeavors. An example of the strategic engagement this promotes is the partnership formed for the development of the Al Dhafra Solar PV Project,

which, upon completion, will be one of the largest solar power plants in the world, significantly increasing Abu Dhabi's renewable energy capacity (Salimi et al., 2022).

Simultaneously, the Department of Energy is exploring regulatory frameworks to accommodate and encourage smaller-scale renewable energy projects, indicating its recognition of the value of distributed energy resources and community-based initiatives in achieving Abu Dhabi's clean energy objectives. Such regulatory adjustments are crucial for a more diversified and resilient energy sector.

Challenges and Opportunities for Policy Adjustment

Abu Dhabi's ambitious renewable energy goals present unique challenges and opportunities, especially in balancing large-scale solar projects with the integration of smaller, decentralized initiatives. The main challenge lies in the preference for large-scale projects, which, while effective in rapidly increasing renewable energy capacity, may overlook the potential of distributed generation, as noted above (Mas'ud et al., 2018).

Indeed, an opportunity for policy adjustment lies in encouraging just this distributed generation, which could serve as a valuable complement to Abu Dhabi's large-scale solar projects. For instance, incentivizing rooftop solar installations on residential and commercial buildings could contribute to the energy mix while empowering communities and individuals to participate in the renewable energy transition (Hussain et al., 2022). Moreover, Abu Dhabi benefits significantly from investments in energy storage technologies and smart grid infrastructure. Such innovations are crucial to overcoming the challenges associated with renewable energy, such as intermittence and the complexities of integrating various energy sources into a cohesive grid. A practical example of this forward-thinking approach could be the

deployment of battery storage systems alongside solar projects, enhancing the reliability and efficiency of renewable energy utilization (Mas'ud et al., 2018).

By focusing on these areas, Abu Dhabi can create a more flexible and resilient energy system that supports its large-scale renewable ambitions and fosters innovation, community participation, and sustainability in its energy sector. Policy adjustments that embrace distributed generation and advances in storage and grid technologies will be instrumental in realizing Abu Dhabi's vision for a sustainable and diversified energy future.

Discussion

The findings show that both Dubai and Abu Dhabi have made policy decisions that continue to prove effective in promoting solar PV energy production. However, implementing solar PV policies in Dubai and Abu Dhabi requires navigating various challenges, from regulatory hurdles and financial constraints to the technical limitations of integrating large-scale solar power production into existing energy infrastructures. Both emirates have encountered difficulties in allocating land for large solar projects, ensuring grid stability with increasing shares of intermittent solar power, and securing sufficient investment to fund ambitious renewable energy targets (Praveen et al., 2020). Solutions have been multifaceted and innovative, reflecting the complexities of the energy transition. Regulatory reforms have streamlined project approvals and incentivized private-sector participation. Financial models, including green bonds and solar leasing programs, have made solar investment more attractive (Al Naqbi et al., 2019). Both Dubai and Abu Dhabi have strongly emphasized building local

capacity in solar technology through partnerships with academic institutions and international companies, ensuring that renewable energy sector growth is sustainable and inclusive.

Dubai's effective solar PV policies facilitate active participation across societal segments, making renewable energy accessible and beneficial at the individual level. This approach democratizes energy production and fosters a strong sense of community involvement and responsibility in advancing sustainability. While also aiming for sustainability, Abu Dhabi's effective solar PV policies position the emirate as a leader in the renewable energy sector through strategic, high-impact projects. These projects contribute significantly to the UAE's renewable energy goals and enhance Abu Dhabi's global reputation. Together, Dubai's distributed generation model and Abu Dhabi's centralized project focus embody the comprehensive approach taken to renewable energy by the UAE. While each emirate has its unique strengths and faces specific challenges, together, they exemplify the country's multifaceted strategy for achieving sustainability and energy independence.

Limitation

The research predominantly utilizes a qualitative approach to assess policy effectiveness. While this is suitable for understanding the nuances of policy frameworks and stakeholder dynamics, it may not fully capture the quantitative impacts of these policies on solar energy adoption, carbon emissions reduction, and economic outcomes. A more detailed quantitative

analysis could complement the findings by providing measurable policy success or failure indicators.

Conclusion

This paper has examined the efficacy of Dubai's and Abu Dhabi's solar PV energy policies and suggested ways to improve these policies. Given remarkable recent advances in renewable energy, there is still significant scope for research in areas such as comparative policy analysis, the integration of emerging technologies, and the long-term sustainability of energy programs. Following a synthesis of peer-reviewed literature, this paper argues that Abu Dhabi should allow homeowners, businesses, and industrial operators to install solar panels and connect them to the grid as a sustainable addition to its solar PV energy policies.

The findings of this study offer actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders in improving future UAE policies. By assessing how successfully each city has implemented its energy goals, this study provides valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of their respective policies.

This paper's comparative analysis of the solar PV policies in Dubai and Abu Dhabi has emphasized their respective strategic approaches to adopting renewable energy. It has examined each city's policy frameworks and stakeholder engagement strategies using peer-reviewed scholarly articles, revealing significant differences in policy effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and implementation outcomes, including Dubai's focus on distributed energy production and Abu Dhabi's focus on large-scale projects. It contributes to the broader field of renewable energy policy analysis by providing insights into the factors influencing policy success in the context of the UAE's energy transition goals (Attoye et al., 2022).

While this study recommends further investigation into enhancing solar PV energy policies in the UAE, its results support the value of policies focusing on sustainability, security, and stakeholder support. Policymakers and stakeholders can use this information to make informed decisions, which could enhance the UAE's overall solar PV energy plan. The UAE's policies regarding the energy transition could, in turn, serve as a model for other countries looking to develop their renewable energy sectors.

The findings suggest that future research should look beyond conventional renewable energy technologies to create a supportive policy environment that promotes a diversified and integrated energy mix, ensuring it remains clean, cost-effective, and reliable. In particular, there is significant potential for studies examining the long-term impacts of such energy strategies, especially with regard to their influence on energy security, economic development, and social welfare.

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